

DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN POLICY OF THE RUSSIAN FEDERATION AT THE BEGINNING OF THE XXI CENTURY

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Abstract.

Since the end of the Cold War, the Russian Federation has experienced a painful transition. During this period, complex processes took place in the economic, social and political fields. As a result of these processes, several uncertainties began to arise in domestic and foreign policy. One of the problems that the Yeltsin administration has not been able to solve is the inability to stop the narrowing of Russia's geopolitical sphere of influence. By 1991, the western borders of the country were reduced from the middle of Germany to 200 km from Moscow. A controversial situation arose over Japan over the Kuril Islands in the east. In addition, the country separated from its allies in Eastern Europe, the Middle East, Latin America, Asia, the Pacific, and other regions. On the other hand, competition between Moscow and the West, which was due to ideological reasons during the Cold War, continued. The above picture represents the main dilemmas that Russia faced in the post-Soviet period. President Vladimir Putin has developed new approaches to overcome the economic, administrative and political problems that have arisen during the transition period, and to eliminate shortcomings in foreign policy. Following a pragmatic line, the administration of Vladimir Putin first improved the economic situation in Russia and took measures to strengthen the influence of the central government in domestic politics. Thus, Russia, having strengthened inside the country, was also able to pursue an effective foreign policy abroad. The article analyzes the priorities of Russian foreign policy at the present stage.

Keywords.

foreign policy, Russia, West, Asian countries, CIS.

Introduction

The Putin administration, in contrast to the Gorbachev-Yeltsin era, began to conduct relations with the West on the axis of pragmatism, not partnership.

The main discussion about Russia's place in the world during the 2000s. was about its position as a great power in a multipolar world [Svarin 2016:131]. The initial positioning of Russia in the world order after the collapse of the Soviet Union involved its interaction with Western countries and integration into Western organizations. Since the turn of the century, the emphasis has been

It focused on the development of new areas of cooperation in the post-Soviet space, such as the Customs Union (CU) and the EAEU in economic matters and the

CSTO in security matters. At the same time, closer relations with other emerging powers, notably China, have been developed through bodies such as the SCO and BRICS.

The foreign policy of the Kremlin, conducted under the leadership of President V. Putin, which differs from the tendencies of the new Westernism, extreme Eurasianism and Russian nationalism, can be characterized as pragmatic Eurasianism.

The beginning of V. Putin's third presidential term marked a turn in Russian foreign policy discourse. The concept of the foreign policy of the Russian Federation during this period was revealed in his article entitled "Russia and the Changing World", published in the newspaper "Moskovsky Komsomolets" dated February 27. Declaring that world security will not be achieved without Russia, V. Putin stated that the goal of Russian foreign policy is to achieve strategic goals that correspond to the political position, historical role and development of the country. The Russian leader noted that he would work to create a global system in accordance with the new geopolitical realities, while emphasizing the need to comply with international law. He accused the US and NATO of violating international sovereignty and thereby violating state sovereignty. V. Putin announced that Russia will not allow the implementation of the Libyan scenario in Syria. He also signaled that Moscow would deepen cooperation with Beijing in the context of common global priorities. V. Putin announced the need for a new global vision of nuclear weapons, as well as decisions on Afghanistan and international terrorism. The Russian leader also stressed that Moscow would respond to US efforts to expand NATO and missile defense systems.

The "New Concept of the Foreign Policy of the Russian Federation" published on the official website of the Russian Foreign Ministry aroused great interest among experts. First of all-

Go, this is a document that allows a large state to clarify its place and status, taking into account the geopolitical changes taking place in the modern world. One of the main provisions of the concept: "Russia must build its foreign policy in a rapidly changing world." The main provisions of the document are formulated with this condition in mind. In a rapidly changing world, foreign policy should emphasize two aspects. First of all, a flexible and multi-vector model of activity should be preferred. Secondly, it should be assumed that the main force against Russia is the West and, above all, the United States. These theses play an important role in the overall approach of the concept.

In modern conditions, the role of Russia is seen in "playing a balanced role in international relations." The current foreign policy course of Moscow sets the task of achieving this goal. Of course, it takes a lot of effort to play the role of balance on a global scale. The concept defines the main goals of the country's foreign policy: first, to help the world economy survive. For this, Russia must actively contribute to the formation of a fair and democratic economic, trade, monetary and financial system throughout the world. Secondly, to fight the attempts of others to interfere in their internal affairs. Moscow will strive to respect human rights and freedoms. However, the historical, cultural and national characteristics of each state must be taken into account. The concept also includes methods which Russia will use to solve these problems. In an official document, Moscow uses the term "soft power" for the first time, referring to the program of action that Putin announced in his article: "Russia and World Heritage"¹.

According to the current foreign policy approach of the Kremlin, Russia is becoming the pole of a multipolar international system dominated by cooperation interest-based value. Taking into account the rise in oil prices, control over energy resources becomes an essential element of foreign policy. In addition to energy policy, examples such as increasing the export of arms and technologies, improving the economy, supporting the activities of Russian companies and Russian citizens abroad can be cited as examples of the pragmatic practice of the Russian Federation. V. Putin summed up the basic philosophy of Russia's foreign policy as follows: "The independence of our foreign policy is beyond doubt. The basis of this foreign policy is pragmatism, economic efficiency and the priority of national problems."

National security documents and official statements emphasize that Russia is a Eurasian country. Only a strong, efficient, democratic state that can protect the rights and economic freedoms of its citizens and provide them with suitable living conditions can respond to external challenges. The need for this strong state is explained for pragmatic reasons. Supporters of this approach argue that Russian foreign policy is based on realism and pragmatism, and the country's current capabilities are effectively used to influence global conditions. Supporters of this model, whose main goal is to ensure the geopolitical independence of the country by strengthening Russia and its position in the international arena, oppose concessions in exchange for economic sanctions and European integration.

- Strengthen Russia's leading positions in the post-Soviet space, in particular, by economic means.

• Efficient use of geopolitical resources inherited from the Soviet Union. This principle is to keep nuclear weapons as a deterrent, to use the veto power granted by the UN Security Council, in accordance with national interests, use Russian natural resources in export and transit, foreign policy, Russian military bases. strengthening and maintaining relations with former allies.

• Maintaining Russia's relations with the Western world on a new basis.

• To establish a balance in parallel with the development of relations between Russia and Western Asia. In this regard, China, India, Türkiye and Iran stand out.

• Use of Russian transit capacities.

Relations with Western countries

Despite all the reactions of radical Eurasians, Moscow was an active partner in Washington's antiterrorist campaign. Russia has also demanded that US companies increase their investment in Russia, especially in energy, in exchange for US support. In addition, Moscow wanted to have wider influence on issues such as NATO expansion and Alliance operations. As a result of the rapprochement after September 11, the Russian Federation has achieved some success. The rapprochement between Moscow and Washington is also reflected in Russia-NATO relations.

In fact, it is difficult to talk about common interests that would require a long-term alliance between Russia and the Western world. Historically, culturally and geopolitically, there are deep fault lines between Russia and the Western world. A similar situation exists for the general perception of threats by the parties. A security issue that is vital for one may be an opportunity for another.

The post-9/11 picture of Russia's relations with the Western world was only a cyclical convergence. This convergence, which was formed on the axis of short-term interests, did not rest on a solid foundation. In fact, in the future, relations between Moscow and Washington turned into a game based on competition. In fact, Russia could not find the support it hoped for from the West in some matters, and this situation affected Moscow's relations with the West in general and the United States in particular. Back at the Munich Conference, President V. Putin openly and sharply criticized the one-sided course of the United States. According to him, the US has crossed its national borders in every way, and this is also evident in the economic, political, cultural and educational policies imposed by the US on other countries.

The US is not the only country against which Russia opposes. Russia also warns the EU and reminds that the decision to use force will be legal only if

approved by the UN. At the same time, it is emphasized that the EU and NATO cannot replace the UN.

Relations between the EU and Russia began to take shape on a new basis. Russia has made the EU dependent on itself in the energy sector [Leonard, Popescu 2009: 7]. This period saw a steady increase in trade relations between the EU and Russia. Russia has become the EU's most important foreign trade partner after the US and China. 84% of Russian gas exports go to European countries [Gomart 2009: 4].

The Russian Federation also signed the Kyoto Protocol, to which the United States and China are not parties. During this period, Moscow did not oppose the European Security and Defense Policy established by the EU since 1999. In the post-Cold War period, official EU and Russian security documents did not contain statements that posed a threat to each other.

Russia opposes the EU's policy of expanding integration with Europe as part of the "Expanding New European Neighborhood Policy". Instead, Russia advocates mutual rapprochement based on the fundamental interests of both sides. On the other hand, the US policy of NATO expansion weakens ties and trust between Russia and the West and undermines the progressive development of EU relations with Russia [Monaghan 2009: 1-2].

Moscow prefers to move closer to countries such as France and Germany that oppose US hegemony in order to capitalize on conflicts in the transatlantic alliance. However, the relations that have developed in the triangle, Ros-this-Germany-France, consist of cooperation arising from the current conjuncture.

Relations with Asian countries

The Kremlin has significantly expanded the Asian dimension of Russian foreign policy. Due to the "special" nature of Tokyo-Washington and the Kuril Islands relations, there has been no comprehensive progress in Moscow-Tokyo relations. However, a similar situation cannot be said about Moscow-Beijing and Moscow-Delhi relations. The Asian policy of the Russian Federation, aimed at creating a multipolar world order by destroying US influence in the region, consists of the following strategies: develop strategic cooperation with China and India, expand political and economic relations with Japan and create a new Asian triangle within the Russia-China-India triangle . It also aimed to develop relations with former allies such as the Islamic world, the countries of Southeast Asia, North Korea and Vietnam.

The strategic alliance with China is the most important dimension of Russia's expansion in Asia. The strategic alliance with this country is an important

achievement of Russian foreign policy in the Asian direction. NATO's expansion into a global organization, the US military presence in Asia, and the US-Japan Security Alliance are seen by both countries as common security concerns. Moscow is primarily trying to improve economic relations with China and bring Russian manufactured goods to the Chinese market, thereby balancing the trade deficit against this country and diversifying the energy market. Thanks to the progress made in the economic sphere, it aims to control the effectiveness of Beijing in the region. In addition, in response to the nuclear energy agreement signed between the United States and India,

The most important event in Russian-Chinese relations is the transformation membership of the Shanghai Five in the SCO. Its SCO members have stated that their ultimate goal is to create an economic and security bloc similar to the EU in Central Asia. The organization seeks to become an active participant in the determination of global and regional policies. This activity manifested itself as a direct opposition to the course of the United States.

However, there are some points that can overshadow the strategic relationship of two historically antagonistic states, such as Russia and China, with different regional interests. First of all, China can determine the strategy of oil supplies for political influence in Central Asia and the Caucasus and the use of energy resources in this region. In this case, it is quite possible that Russian-Chinese relations will change from long-term cooperation to competition. Russia's ability to develop relations with the West could affect the strategic partnership between Moscow and Beijing. In addition, the unilateral US policy in the world, the strategic relationship established with Taiwan and Japan, and the arms embargo imposed by the West are currently bringing China closer to Russia.

On the other hand, a common threat perception may not be enough to achieve a strategic partnership between countries. Differentiating US policy towards the two countries can lead to both balancing and weakening of both countries. On the other hand, despite the progress made in the economic and commercial areas, especially in energy, some unevenness in this area is not lost. Moscow turned to third world countries as another foreign policy initiative. During this period, relations with the countries of Southeast Asia and the Middle East were developed. Moscow is also seeking to develop its relations with the Islamic world. Russia received observer status in the OIC and demonstrated its determination to improve relations with the Islamic world. In particular, the strategic dimension of relations with Iran was strengthened. Both Iran and Russia are concerned about the growing US influence in the region. Relations between the two states have intensified with

Russia's support for Iran's nuclear program, despite the embargo imposed against Tehran. The current state of Western-Iranian relations and Iran's nuclear program have brought Tehran closer to Moscow. In line with this approach, Russia continues to support Iran's nuclear weapons program. In response to US actions, Moscow stepped up support for Tehran's nuclear activities.

Relations with CIS countries

One of the most important foreign policy goals of the Russian Federation is the restoration of Moscow's role in the post-Soviet space. During this period, Central Asia became a region in which Moscow significantly increased its influence. The Kremlin's strategy is based on the idea of keeping the countries of Central Asia within Russia's sphere of influence by increasing Moscow's economic influence over them.

Another region, which is one of the geopolitical priorities of the Russian Federation, is the South Caucasus. The most important aspect of Russian policy in the South Caucasus is the Russian-

Azerbaijani relations. In recent decades, a high level of high-level diplomatic visits between Moscow and Baku has been achieved, progress has been made in the economic, trade and cultural fields. During this period, relations between Moscow and Tbilisi became more tense. The Kremlin recognized the independence of Abkhazia and South Ossetia. Tbilisi, having announced its withdrawal from the CIS, was completely removed from Moscow. Of the countries of the South Caucasus, only Armenia is a strategic ally of Russia. However, this alliance eventually led to Armenia's unilateral dependence on Russia. During this period, bilateral agreements increased Yerevan's dependence on Moscow in the economic sphere, as well as in matters of defense and security.

Russia's relations with Belarus, Moscow's closest ally, have reached a new level. According to integration, two countries have implemented about thirty joint programs and projects in various fields such as economy, ecology, defense and social development. Thus, in response to the eastward expansion of the EU and NATO, Russia has also created a buffer zone between these forces and itself, which could reduce the potential for threats. However, Russian-Ukrainian relations have become the main stumbling block in the post-Soviet space. Today, Russian-Ukrainian relations are very tense due to a number of fundamental problems. Ukraine's foreign policy has shifted to a purely pro-Western line.

The integration project of Russia in the post-Soviet space, the EAEU influences the political choice of countries. He shares them in terms of which development

paths they are committed to, such as Armenia's rejection and Ukraine's implementation of the Association Agreement (AA) with the EU.

Despite the increasingly prominent role of security in the discourse of the world order, economic discourses in Russian foreign policy are important and cannot be ignored. However, reflections on economic cooperation are more about aspirations for the future than the actual achievements of the Eurasian integration project.

Conclusion

The foreign policy philosophy of the Russian Federation is not based on radical Eurasian views. Moscow, adopting a pragmatic

Eurasianism as a synthesis of various political movements continues its foreign policy in this direction. The rapprochement between Moscow and Washington after the events of September 11 was the result of this political understanding. However, US actions to maintain a unipolar system and the Kremlin's goal of a multipolar world put an end to this rapprochement. During this period, relations with the EU developed in many areas, and special relations were established with Germany and France. Moscow tried to limit the actions of the United States in a unipolar system and create an anti-American geopolitical axis in the third world. The result of this policy is special relations with China, India, Iran, Iraq, Syria, North Korea and Latin American countries. Russian-Chinese relations are turning into a strategic alliance. Moscow is also pursuing a more active policy based on bilateral relations with the CIS countries. As a result of his strategy, the strategic depth of relations with Belarus, Armenia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan and Uzbekistan has been increased. While these countries became more dependent on Moscow, relations with Azerbaijan, Moldova and Turkmenistan developed. However, Georgia and Ukraine have moved further away from Moscow.

Thus, Russia today is one of the leading players in international politics.

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